

THE PURPOSE OF THE TOURIST ROUTE DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGY AND ITS TASKS IN ARCHITECTURAL-LANDSCAPE PROJECTS

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Annotation. In this article, the technologies of development of tourist routes, their integral connection with landscape and road systems, the main concepts were determined and the terminological apparatus was formed. The concept of "tourist route" is defined, the interpretation of the terms "tourist route" and "tourist roads", types of tourist routes and their formation are studied. The planning of tourist routes should be organized in such a way as to create an opportunity to choose routes that effectively use available resources based on tourist routes. On the other hand, it is explained that the tourist routes are considered as a thematic route for tourists.

Key words: concept, tourist resource, historical, object, tourist route, direction, landscape, green architecture, internal system, system of tourist excursion services, tourist-recreational, standards, area, road systems, ecological tourism, urban development.

Uzbekistan is attracting the attention of the world community due to its many historical-architectural and archaeological monuments and its rapid development. If we look at history, Uzbekistan was located on the path of trade, travelers, missionaries, geographers, and conquerors of the Great Silk Road. Today, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the fascinating tourist destinations for tourists interested in culture, history and exotic countries.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5611 dated January 5, 2019, APPENDIX 1, CONCEPT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN 2019-2025, CHAPTER 3. The main directions of tourism development, in paragraph 2: development of tourism infrastructure and related infrastructure in all regions of the country, taking into account the needs and requirements of tourists, in particular[1]:

- taking into account the demand, along with the construction of new accommodation facilities and the reconstruction of existing ones, as well as adjacent infrastructure (public catering facilities, transport-logistics structures, entertainment facilities industry, cultural and sports institutions, tourist exhibition facilities, etc.) development of comprehensive measures for the development of the tourism industry aimed at development;

- to simplify the mechanism of implementation of projects related to the construction of hotels and other tourism infrastructure facilities, to create additional conditions for entrepreneurs to improve the quality of their services, as well as to encourage the attraction of world-famous hotel business brands to Uzbekistan;
- step-by-step development of accommodation facilities, encouraging the construction of large, medium and small hotels and hostels, and paying special attention to the reconstruction and modernization of existing hotels;
- creation of street infrastructure (passageways, sidewalks, small architectural forms, sanitary-hygienic stations, improvement elements for people with physical disabilities, etc.), including in tourism and recreation centers, taking into account modern international standards;
- implementation and development of a single unified system of tourism navigation, establishment of unified indicators of tourism navigation on streets, areas, within buildings and structures considered as objects of tourism demonstration, vehicles and networks, and highways is discussed separately.

Even today, Samarkand is a living link connecting the present and the ancient past. Samarkand is ready to share its famous cultural heritage sites, interesting and unique natural resources.

It is not for nothing that the development of tourism activity is reflected in the priority directions of economic development and liberalization in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In addition, 2019 is the year of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan APPENDIX 5 to Decree No. PF-5781 of August 13 "Investment proposals for the construction and reconstruction of highways along the tourist routes of the Republic of Uzbekistan were made, and the road map was developed, approved tourism to serves to a certain extent in carrying out research in the implementation of the tasks defined in the Law on "[2].

Modern studies of the recreation environment are devoted to the study of the regional tourist system and tourist-recreational zones. Most of the researches belong to the fields of geography (comprehensive study of recreation zoning) and tourism sciences (internal system of tourist institutions, system of tourist excursion services), as well as humanities, which study the basics of cultural tourism.

In this article, the works of scientific researchers of various directions, which reveal some aspects in the field of tourism architecture research, foreign scientists on the architecture of tourist routes and complexes Rainer Jelinek, Jan Specht, Hans Jeschke, Peter Mandl, R. Sharpley, Marlien Lawrence, Ivana

Vukadinovic, V.A. Nefedov, L. Yu. Smykovskaya, Ye.P. Golubeva, K.V. Lazarev Ye.K. Bulatova, V.V. Aurov, G.S. Zaikin, H. Shenasa, D.M. By Bayramova, V.A. Nielsen, O.M. Salimov, M.Q. Ahmedov, A.A. Saidov, A.O. Hasanov, A.S. Uralov, L.A. Kamilova, M. Tokhtakhodzaeva, K.D. Rakhimov, N.V. Drobchenko, K.D. Sattarova, Kh.Kh. Kamilova and others conducted scientific research.

In addition, a number of researchers are conducting a number of scientific researches on the development and improvement of the methodological foundations of ecological tourism, the rational use of natural resources, and the development and improvement of the regulatory and legal framework of ecological tourism. Including Ye. Boo, H. Ayala, Ye. Matthews, A.K. Alymov, M.T. Covered in the work of Alieva et al. Today, the development of tourism development programs based on the formation of architectural environments of tourist infrastructure and the fact that research work on their implementation is not being carried out at the present time shows the need to study this topic.

Tourist routes - the word "route" means a defined, designated path. The word "route" is not only relevant in the field of tourism, but also refers to the permanent, regular movement of people to a certain direction, or rather, to a certain geographic destination, which is not related to tourism[3]. A person chooses a means of transportation depending on the distance and proximity of the route. The object of study of tourist routes is a geographical address related to routes. The tourist route is to take the tourist to the tourist resource located in the geographical location, place chosen by the tourist, taking into account and fulfilling the needs of the tourist and bringing the tourist back to the original destination[5].

Determining the place of tourist route architectural environment objects in the formation of urban planning compositions;

Development of a database on the functional, size-structural, structural and planning features of the establishment of tourist centers in the Samarkan-Jizzah region, taking into account regional factors, in accordance with modern requirements;

methods of using architectural monuments, objects of cultural heritage and their elements in creating the architectural environment of tourist routes and centers, developing the principles of forming the architectural environment of a tourist center;

improving the principles of organizing architectural environment objects in increasing the socio-economic efficiency of tourist routes and centers;

using computer programs to prepare schematic drawings of architectural objects of the tourist environment and create a database on them.

In addition to this, Samarkand-Jizzah tourist areas and objects of routes are to create an architectural environment.

The characteristics of the formation and organization of the architectural environment of tourism, the ways of development, the possibility of adapting them to the practice of regional architecture and urban planning, as well as the organization of design materials, the methodological bases are general scientific methods, which are: statistical, comparative, electronic materials and it is recommended to use methods such as analysis of architectural projects, observation, systematization of scientific data, comparative analysis and generalization[5].

The field research method is used to study the objects of the existing architectural environment in the Samarkand-Jizzakh region M39 road, tourism and recreation areas.

The results of the study and analysis of the Samarkand-Jizzah M39 road are as follows:

Based on the touristic resource potential of Samarkand-Jizzah regions, scenario approach methods have been developed for touristic routes;

scientific knowledge about historical and theoretical conditions of formation of touristic and recreational areas, architectural environment for tourism has been expanded;

To obtain socio-economic benefits from the introduction of the main results of studies on the development of the parameters, quantitative characteristics of tourism objects, the method of evaluating the tourist potential into the practice of regional architecture, in order to organize and develop the tourist architectural environment in areas with tourist potential necessary conditions are formed;

Proposals for the effective placement of recreational areas and the creation of composite solutions for other tourist objects on the tourist routes in the Samarkand-Jizzah region have been developed;

Concepts of creation, reconstruction and tourism development of modern tourist centers of Samarkand-Jizzah region were created;

methods of using objects of cultural heritage and architectural monuments and their elements have been improved in the design of prospective master plans of tourist routes and tourist centers.

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